

TIMING OF MARRIAGE

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Abstract:

Predicting the timing of events is a challenge for many astrologers. Marriages are made in heaven. But there is a certain age limit for Boys and girls. If it's exactly correct, the age for marriage of boys will be between 25 to 35 years and of girls 20 to 30 years. Some marriages take place earlier to above said ages. Here we will examine whether the marriage took place at the correct age.

Key Words: Dasa/Bukthi, Transit of Planets, Upa Pada Lagna, Ashtaka Vargha, Bindu, Sodya Panda, Varusha Jaathak (Yearly Horoscope), Pancha Varkiya Phala, Suba Arkala, Asuba Arkala, Vivaha Sagam, Ithasala Yoga

There are many ways and means to find out the timing of marriage-

- We should come to know the Main and Sub periods.
- Through Navamsa
- From upa padha lagna.
- Through the transit position of planets.
- By finding through Ashtaka varga.
- Varsha Pal through yearly Horoscope.
- Through transit position in Navamsa.

Through each one of the above points we will see one by one the timing of the marriage with few case studies.

2-1 In the Main and sub-period of the following planets – 7th house (Kalatra Bhava). The planets placed in the 7th house, the Planets aspect 7th Bhava and the Dasa, Bukthi period of 7th lord. In these Dasa, bhukti periods the marriage of the native may take place. The 7th bhava should be calculated from Lagna and chandra lagna.

2-2 finding out the timing of marriage through Navamsa to find out the futures of married life. The current Dasa planet should have connection with the Navamsa lagna or the lagna lord or there should be suba – arkala. The planets in 2, 4 and 11th house are called "Suba - arkala". Benefics make benefic Arkala and malefic planets make malefic (asuba) arkala.

The planets in 12, 10 and 3rd houses obstruct the formation of arkala. Bukthi lord should get connected with 7th lord from navamsa lagna, or there should be the planet position for Suba - arkala.

There should be connection between the Kama trine houses 3, 7, 11, 8 from the 7th house or Venus to the Chandra lagna or at least there should be Suba - arkala.

3-0 Aruda bhava of 12th bhava is known as Upa Padha Lagna. Say the ascendant is Gemini. The 12th house is Taurus and the lord of that sign is Venus. Venus is in Cancer, the 3rd bhava from Taurus. When counted from Cancer 3rd bhava Virgo is the Upa padha lagna.

To cite another example the Moon is the 12th bhava lord to Leo. The Moon is in Sagittarius which is 6th house from Cancer sign. So, Sagittarius is the Upa padha lagna.

3-1. when the 2nd sign comes on Jupiter Star the marriage of the native takes place. The trine sign of the 2nd sign of the Upa Padha lagna comes on Jupiter Star or the aspect of Jupiter marriage of the native takes place. Here we should also consider the aspect of Jaimini Sutra. In the Jaimini sutra the Moveable sign aspect fixed sign, fixed sign aspect the Moveable sign. The Common sign or dual sign aspect the other common sign.

The planets in the Upa Padha lagna narrate the character of the spouse. The benefic planets denote the spouse from gentlefolk and malefic planets denote a worst or bad spouse. If both suba and asuba planets denote the spouse as to have a mixed character spouse.

Finding the Timing of Marriage through Transit:

Though all the planets are concerned for one's wedding to happen, especially the planets Saturn, Jupiter and Rahu play a very important role in their transit. So, we have to decide it with these planets. When these planets in their Dasa / Bukthi period transit through these houses 2nd house is family, 4th the well being, health, comforts, etc. 7th house denotes spouse, partner. 8th house Mangalya sthana (for woman) wedlock (for Man) 9 is Bhagya sthan. 5th house denotes love, happiness, the chance of the native is more possible.

Through Astavarga - The Bindus (Venus Binnashtavarga) in the 7th house with respect to the house where Venus is placed. This Bindu should be multiplied by the Sodya Pinda of Venus and the result should be divided by 27. The result we get should be counted from the Star Ashwini, and when Jupiter transits there the native will get married. If the multiplied result is divided by 12 and that balance number should be counted from the Aries sign. When Jupiter transits there or aspect the Aries sign, the marriage will take place. We must also see the sign where Venus has more Bindus.

Through Varusha Pal – The year lord is Venus. Muntha lord is also Venus. Venus has full Pancha vargiya Bala and is strong.

In the natal horoscope Venus is the 7th lord. In the yearly horoscope Venus is in the Ascendant and also the Year lord. Muntha dasa of Venus is from 19-12-1988 to 20-4-1988. The native's marriage took place on 4 – 7 – 1988. This is ensured by vivaha Sagam. The Vivaha sagam = Venus° - Saturn ° + Ascendant° = 202°-44' - 234° - 06' + 195°-28' = 398°-12' - 234°-06' - 164° - 06' i.e. 14° - 06' is at Virgo sign. In Varusha Jathak, 7th lord Mars are in that Virgo Sign. This point should be taken as it is from the earlier Sign. Age also should be counted from the previous Sign.

- In a natal chart if Jupiter is at 1° and Saturn is at 3° these two planets are to be considered as in the previous sign.
- In natal chart if Rahu is with Mars, or in the next sign to Mars, the 4th house from Mars is considered as the important point.
- In natal chart if Saturn is in 7th house from Rahu and or Mars, then the 4th house from Mars is considered as the important point.
- If Mars is in mutual transfer with some other planet, it should be considered as it is in its own house and that is the important point.
- If Mars is with Rahu and Mars is retrograde then Mars is considered as to be in the previous sign.
- Delineation through Navamsa Transit – We see the transit position in Rasi chakra. But to see the timing of marriage the Navamsa transit will give a clear picture. The same principle / rule is followed in navamsa transit also.

Case Study 1:

DOB - 23-10-1964 – TOB – 9 - 10 AM, POB – Madurai

		Ju, Mo	Ra	Ma	Ke			
Sat	Rasi – D1		Ma	Asc//	Navamsa–D9			
			Ve	JU, Mo, Me				
Ke	Asc//	Me, Su		Ve	Su, Sat	Ra		

Planets position –

- Asc – Jeshta – 3 Sun – Chitra – 4 Moon - Kiruthika – 2
- Mars – Aslesha - Mercury – Swathi – 2 Jup – Kiruthika – 2
- Venus – Uttara Phalguni – 1 Sat – Dhanishta – 4, Rahu – Mrigashira-3
- Ketu – Moola – 1.

Case Study 2:

Dasa / Bukthi rule – 7th lord is Venus, Jupiter and the Moon are in 7th house. At the time of marriage these three planets Dasa was not running. Venus is in the Sun's house Leo. There is no planet in the 7th house from the Moon. Saturn aspect 7th lord Mars.

- The Sun Dasa is completed at the age of 3.
- The Moon Dasa is completed at the age of 13.
- Mars Dasa is completed at the age of 20.

Rahu Dasa was running in the marriageable age of the Girl. Rahu is in Gemini, the house of Mercury. The dispositor of Venus is the Sun and the dispositor of Dasa lord Rahu, is Mercury who is placed in the 12th house. So, we can come to the conclusion that the marriage will take place in the Rahu dasa. As 2nd lord Jupiter is in the 7th house of a partner, we can say that in the sub – period of Jupiter the marriage will be conducted.

Finding through Navamsa:

Navamsa Lagna is Sagittarius and the lord is Jupiter. The current Dasa is Rahu Dasa. In Navamsa from Rahu, Jupiter is in the 4th house. i. e. Rahu forms arkala to Jupiter. So, in Rahu Dasa the marriage will be conducted. Next, we will see the Bukthi. In navamsa Gemini is the 7th house. There is no planet in this sign. With the 7th lord Mercury, the Moon and Jupiter are there. In that the Moon Dasa has crossed in the childhood of the native. Now the current bukthi is of Jupiter, are promises for the marriage. Next, comes the Andhara period. In navamsa the 3rd, 7th and 11th houses from 7th house and the Sun, Jupiter and Mars are the lords respectively. The Kalthira karaka is Venus. There are no planets in the houses 3. 7. 11. Jupiter is debilitated. 2nd lord Saturn in 12th house aspect the Dhana bhava. In 2nd house Mercury, 7 and 10th lord, Jupiter, the lagna, 4th lord, the Moon is the 8th lord and the 7th lord Mercury is in the 8th house. So, there is every chance of getting married in the Andhara of Mercury. This marriage was held in the Mercury Andhara on 4 – 7 – 1988, Monday.

Upa Pada lagna – Gemini falls as upa pada lagna in the Rasi chakra. The 2nd Rasi from Upa Pada lagna is Cancer. When Jupiter Transits over any one of these Rasis Cancer, Scorpio, Pisces the marriage will take place. From the Taurus rasi the Jupiter aspects the ascendant. The marriage took place in the year 1988. This rule does not match here. Finding the time of marriage through Transit of planets.

Ma		Ju, Me Ve	Su
Ra, Mo	4 - 7 - 1988		
	Rasi		Ke
Sat	Asc//		

The Sun – 78°. The Moon – 315°. Mars – 331°. Mercury – 57°. Jupiter – 33°. Venus – 50°. Saturn – 244°. Rahu – 323°. Ketu – 143°. Birth Lagna Scorpio, the transit Jupiter aspects Janma lagna Saturn is in the place of family and aspect the 11th house. Jupiter too aspects the same place. Dasa lord Rahu – is in its own star and aspects the 12th house and Mars aspects the place of gain. So, the aspect of all the three planets Jupiter, Saturn and Mars is in the 11th house. Dasa lord Rahu, Bukthi lord Jupiter, Anthara lord mercury, Venus these three lords are in the 7th house.

Example 1: Vivaha

After finding it from navamsa, and Dasa, Bukthi and Anthara lord we should select and examine some days which anthara lord coincide in the transit.

4 - 7 - 1988

Month lord the Sun is in Rahu Star. ---- Rahu is the Dasa lord.

Day lord is The Moon – in Rahu Star --- Rahu is the Dasa lord

Mars is in Jupiter Star – Jupiter is the Bukthi Lord.

Mercury is in the Mars Star.

Lagna lord is Mars.

Jupiter is in the star of Sun

Venus is in the Star of the Moon.

Saturn is in the Star of Ketu.

Rahu is in the star of Jupiter - bhukti lord is Jupiter.

Ketu is in the Venus star.

Here dasa lord Rahu is in the bukthi lord Jupiter’s star, Jupiter is in the star of the Sun, the Anthara Lord Mercury is in the lagna lord Mars Star. The Moon is in Rahu star through Ashtakavarga. In Venus Ashtakavarga the bindu of the 7th house from Venus is 3 bindus. The Sodya pinda is – 114. So, 114 X 3 = 342. 342/27 = 12 and the balance is 8 is Jeshta star. The trine stars are Revathi / Aslesha. 342 / 12 = 28 and the balance are 6 which show Virgo, Capricorn and Gemini signs. When the transit of Jupiter crosses these Signs the marriage may take place. But, this rule has not come true. Still you may see that the Moon and the Sun are in the star of Rahu.

Finding through Varusha Jaathak:

- The sign where Venus is in the Natal chart becomes the 7th house of the varusha Jaathak.
- In Varusha Jaathak the year lord should be Venus and should be strong and have the aspect of Jupiter. If it is such, the marriage will take place soon and there will be issues also soon.
- The Lagna lord in natal chart should be strong and the same should be in the 7th house of the Varusha Jaathak.
- If the year lord is Venus and Mars should aspect from the 7th house or if Mars the Varusha lord and aspect of Venus over Mars from the 7th house. If there is inthasaala Yoga, it will be better than the aspect as said above.
- At the time of birth in Varusha Jathak Venus should be in 7th house and the Lagna lord should be in inthasaala yoga.
- In the natal chart the 7th lord should get connected to Venus as year lord in the Varusha Jathaka or get inthaSaala yoga.

Inthasaala Yoga:

- The lagna lord and the kaariya graham get connected by aspect.
- Mutual aspects of the above should be present.
- The fast moving planet should be behind the slow moving planet. If it is 1 degree behind the slow moving planet, the result of the Kariya graham will be immediate. If it is more the result will be alright. If the slow moving planet is in the beginning degrees of the next sign, the planned work will finish at the end of that year.

		Ju, Mo	
Sat(R)	Natal Chart 23-10-1964 Lady		Ma
		Ve	
Ke	Asc//	Su, Me	

Ra	JU(R)		
	Yearly Chart 1987		
	Sat	Asc// Su, Mo Ve, Me(R)	Ke, Ma

Muntha - 18°46' Libra

Navamsa Transit –

Transit Sun – In Navamsa Chakra in the 7th house- 5th house from the Moon

Transit Moon – In Navamsa Chakra in the 3rd house-

Transit Mars – In Navamsa Chakra in the 4th house- 2nd house from the Moon

Transit Mer – In Navamsa Chakra in the 6th house- 4th house from the Moon

Transit Jup – In Navamsa Chakra in the 6th house- 1st house from Moon

Transit Venus – In Navamsa Chakra in the 1st house- 1st house from Moon

Transit Sat – In Navamsa Chakra in the 3rd house- 11th house from Moon

Transit Ra – In Navamsa Chakra in the 3rd house- 1st house from Moon

Transit Ket – In Navamsa Chakra in the 9th house- 7th house from Moon

In these important planets Rahu, Jupiter, Mercury (Dasa lord, Bukthi lord, Anthara lord) is in the Navamsa lagna and in the 4th house.

In the Nadi System:

Ma		Ju, Mer Ve(R)	Su
Ra, Mo	Star Satbisha 4-7-1988 Asc. Star Poorvapalguni		Asc// Ke
Sat			

		Ju, Mo	Ra
Sat	Natal Chart 23-10-1964 Lady		Ma
Ke	Asc//	Su, Me	

When the transit Jupiter reached the Jupiter in the natal chart the girl got married. Transit Jupiter is in 7th house. The Natal Mars aspect the Transit Mars.

Case Study 2:

6-8-1936 - Madurai

Mo			Ke
Sat	Man. Rasi		Ma,Su
			Mer,Ve
Ra	Asc// Ju(R)		

	Ve	Me	Sat,Ra
	Navamsa		Asc// Mo
Su,Ju			Ma
Ke			

Natal Star – purva Bhadrpad – 4

Balance Dasa – Jupiter – 0 y – 6 M – 13 Days.

Dasa, Bukthi System:

There are no planets in the 7th house. The 7th lord is Venus. Mercury is in the 10th house with an aspect of Saturn. In the 7th house to the Moon there is no planet. Mercury is the 7th lord from the Moon. Venus and Mercury are in the 10th house. The Dasa at the time native attained the age for marriage is –

1934 – 8 – 6

Jupiter Dasa ending at the age – 0 – 4 – 13

1937-2-19

Saturn Dasa 19-0-0 19

1956-2-19

Mercury Dasa 17-0-0

1973-2-15 36

Ketu Dasa 7-0-0

1980-2-15 43

i.e. there are chances of marriage in the Mercury Dasa. Mercury Dasa, Venus bukthi – Saturn bhukti the marriage may take place. In this Venus is 7th lord and kalatra karaka. So, in Venus Bhukti he got married. Mercury Dasa Venus Bukthi from 14-07-1954 to 14-05-1962. His date of the marriage was on 10-07-1961.

Finding through Navamsa – Running Dasa is Mercury. Navamsa lagna is Cancer Sign. Lagna lord the Moon is in 11th house to the Moon. So, Mercury gets Arkala. So, in Mercury Dasa the Marriage took place. In Navamsa the Sun and Jupiter are in 7th house. The 7th house lord is Saturn. Saturn is in the 11th house from Venus and gets the Arkala. So, it is Mercury dasa, Venus Bhukti Marriage occurs. To the 7th lord Jupiter is the 3rd lord, the Moon is in the 7th, 11th lord is Mars, or in Venus in any one of the Andhara dasa marriages will be conducted.

1959 – 07 – 14
 05 – 20
 01 – 21
 02 – 25
 01 – 29
 05 – 03
 04 – 16 1961 – 5 - 8
 05 – 11 1941 – 10 – 19

i.e. in Navamsa in the 7th lord Saturn’s Andhara period (Mercury Dasa, Venus Bukthi and Saturn Andhra) 10 – 7 – 1961 Marriage took place.

Finding through Upa padha lagna – 12th lord Venus is in Leo, the 10th house, from there the 10th house is Taurus. So, Taurus is the Upa Pada lagna. So, when Jupiter transits over Gemini, Libra or Aquarius there is a chance of marriage and it happened When the Jupiter was at 304° - 07’ the At Aquarius.

Case Study 3:

Finding through transit of planets -

			Mo, Ve
Ju, Ke	10 – 07- 1971		Su, Me
Sat	Planets in transit On Monday		Ra
		Ma	

The Sun – 107°, The Moon – 82°, Mars – 156°, Jupiter – 304°. Venus – 63°, Saturn – 297°. Rahu – 149°. Dasa lord Mercury is in the 2nd house from Navamsa Lagna. The Bukthi lord Venus is in the 12th house with Navamsa lagna lord the Moon, the Andhara lord in 7th house and in 9th house to the Moon and in his own house. Jupiter aspects the 2nd and 4th houses of Navamsa.

Saturn aspects the 2nd house of Navamsa.

Mars aspects the 7th house of Navamsa.

The Moon is at 82° in the Star Rahu “Ardra”. Rahu is in the 2nd house. So, this rule is also worked out.

Through Ashtaka vargha method –

7th house from Venus = 3

The Sodhya Pinda = 112.

112 X 3 = 336 / 27 = 13- the balance 15 is Swathi Star.

336 / 12 = 28 – the balance 12.

So, when the transit Jupiter moves on the stars of Rahu(Arudra, Swathi, Sadhabisha) or the signs Pieces, Cancer, Scorpio the Marriage will be conducted. On the date of marriage Jupiter was on Swathi Star in Aquarius. 304° is Satbisha Star, but as per sign it is not correct.

Varusha Jaathak:

		Ma	
Ke	Yearly Horoscope of the year 1960	Su,Me	
Mo		Ve,Ra	
Asc// Ju(R) Sat(R)			

Ma	Ju(R) Mo, Ve	Ke	
	Navamsa		Me
Su			
	Ra		Asc// Sat(R)

Star – Shravana – 1

Muntha 1° - 58’ Scorpio Year lord Venus in the 11th house.

Pancha varkiya Phala Sun – 9 - 29

Moon – 6 - 30

Mars - 6 – 24

Mer - 6 - 51

Jup – 15 – 33

Ven – 5 - 25

Sat – 5 – 34

Muntha Dasa – Ven – Dasa / Ketu Bhukti – 3 – 7 – 1961 to 12 – 7 – 1961.

Conclusion:

In the Natal horoscope Venus and the Varusha phal horoscope Venus are in the same Sign.

- Year lord is Venus.
- In the Natal horoscope the Lagna lord is debilitated. In the yearly Horoscope Venus I in the 7th house from the Moon.
- Inthasaala yoga is formed as Venus is in the 7th house.

Mo			Ke
Sat	Man. Rasi 4 – 8 – 1936 Rasi		Ma,Su
			Mer,Ve
Ra	Asc// Ju(R)		

	Ve	Me	Sat,Ra
	Navamsa		Asc// Mo
Su,Ju			Ma
Ke			

			Mo, Ve
Ju, Ke	10 – 07- 1961		Su,Me
Sat	Date of marriage		Ra
		Ma	

The transiting Jupiter aspect / Mars in the Navamsa.

Transit Saturn is in the 7th house of Navamsa.

In the Natal chart Jupiter, Saturn both the planets are retrograde.

The transit Saturn and the natal Saturn are in Capricorn (3rd house)

The Natal Mars aspects the Transiting Mars.

Navamsa Transit:

- Navamsa lagna lord the Moon transiting through 12th house.
- In Navamsa Jupiter is in Saturn’s house. In that house when Saturn transits there, the marriage will occur.
- In Navamsa 7th lord is Saturn and is in the 7th house in the transit chart.
- In the Navamsa chart 5th and 9th lord Mars is in the 4th house of the Transit chart.
- In the Natal chart Saturn is in the Jupiter star Purva Bhadrapada in the sign Aquarius, in the transit chart Jupiter is in the same Saturn’s house.

Example Chart 3:

Male – 27 – 5 – 1951 Madurai – 09 – 02 PM

Ju.14.12	Me 17.48	Su,12.21 Ma 11.4	Ve.25.24
Mo,9.51 Ra.21.50	Rasi		
			Ke21-50
Asc//			Sat(R) 2.32

Upapada Lagna Leo – 17 – 10. Date of Marriage 14 – 9 – 1980.

Rahu - Dasa – Balance 13 – 3 - 07

	Su, Ma Ra	Ve	
	Navamsa		
Sat			
Mo	Ju	Ke	Asc// Me

Dasa / Bukthi Method:

Date of birth - 1951 – 5 – 27 Age

Rahu Dasa balance - 13 – 3 – 04

1964 – 9 – 06. 13

Jupiter Dasa 16 – 00 - 00

1980 – 09 – 09 29

Saturn Dasa 19 – 00 – 00

1989 – 09 – 09 48.

So, there are chances of Marriage either in the Jupiter dasa or in the beginning of Saturn dasa period. The lord of the 7th house is the Mercury and Saturn Aspects 7th house. From the Moon, Ketu is in the 7th house. The 7th house lord is the Sun. Mars aspects the 7th house. So, in the Dasas or in the Bhukti of Venus, Mercury, Saturn, Ketu, the Sun and Mars, the marriage of this native may take place. Here Saturn dasa there are more chances of marriage. As the Saturn aspect the 7th and the 4th houses there may be delay in the marriage, in the Saturn dasa. Saturn Bhukti is coming as the first bukthi. He is the 2nd lord, Kaaraka, for the family. In Navamsa Saturn Aspects the 7th house. So, the Saturn Dasa and in its own bukthi the marriage will take place.

Upapada Lagna:

Upa Pada Lagna is the Leo sign. When Jupiter transits in Virgo, Capricorn, Taurus Signs the Marriage will take place. When Jupiter comes around all the 12 signs the age of the Native will be 19 years. That is not the proper or suitable age for marriage. So, when Jupiter enters Capricorn or Taurus we may expect the marriage. There may not be a chance for Marriage when Jupiter enters the Sign Capricorn. At the time of marriage on 14 – 9 – 1980, Jupiter was in the sign Leo. Jupiter aspects the mercury, the 2nd lord from Upa Pada lagna. Though Marriage was conducted on 14 – 9 – 1980 when Jupiter enters Leo, the couple should enter into life when Jupiter reaches Virgo sign after crossing Uthrapluni Star.

Astaka Vargam:

Venus Ashtaka Varga – 624, 543, 526, 645.

Sodya Pinda of Venus – 157.

In the 7th house from Venus the Bindu is – 6

Sodya Pinda of Venus – 157. 157 X 6 = 942

i.e. Dhanishta, Mirgasira and Chitra. When Jupiter enters Virgo Marriage was fruitful. The Chitra star is in the Virgo Sign.

Example – case study – 3

Yearly Horoscope – 30

		Su, Me	Asc// Ve(R)
Ke	Yearly Horoscope 27 – 5 -1980		Ju, Ra Ma, Sat
			Mo

Asc-1-26-Mrigasira-3

Sun-12°-21'.Rohini-1

Mo-10°-22'-Swathi-2

Mars-14°-25'-Poorvaphalguni 1

Mer-27°-48'-Mrigasira-2

Jupi-8°-03'-Magha-3

Ven-8°-54'-Arudra

Sat-24°-37'-Poorvaphalguni4

Rahu- 0°-31' - Magha Muntha – 17° – 10', Taurus.

-Ket- 0°-31' - Dhanishta

Venus is in Lagna and the Year lord is also Venus.

Muntha lord is Venus.

Vivaha Sagam – Saturn – Venus Lagna.

Night birth – 144° – 37' -- 68° – 54' + 61°-26'

206° – 03'

68° – 54'

37° – 09'

i.e. In Transit 7° – 09' the Taurus, Rohini Star.

Ju	Me	Ve, Ma	Su
Mo, Ra	Natal chart Rasi		Ke
Asc//			Sat(R)

	Su, Ma Ra	Ve	
	Navamsa		
Sat(R)			
Mo	Ju	Ke	Asc// Me

	Su, Ma Ra	Ve	
	Wedding Day 14 – 9 – 1980 10 - AM		Ve, Ra
Ke			Ju, Su
		Asc//Mo Ma	Sat Me

Pancha varkiya pala

Asc – 24° – 43' Visaka -2

Sun - 27° - 55' Uthrapalguni- 1 - 12 - 42 more strength
Moon - 18° - 57' Swathi - 4 - 5 - 36 fair strength.
Mars - 16° - 58' Swathi - 4 - 7 - 19 fair strength.
Mer - 13° - 09' Hasta - 1 - 15 - 89 more strength.
Jup - 27° - 20' - Uthrapalguni - 11 - 67 more strength.
Ven - 13° - 15' - Poosa - 3 - 7 - 67 fair strength.
Sat - 5° - 31' - Uthrapalguni - 3 - 11 - 80 more strength.
Rahu - 24° - 41' - Aslesha - 3
Ketu - 24° - 41' - Dhanishta - 3

- Transiting Jupiter aspects Natal Ascendant.
- Transiting Saturn aspects Natal Jupiter and the Venus.
- Transiting Rahu aspects Natal Jupiter.
- Dasa lord Saturn is with Natal 7th lord Mercury in transit Chart.

Navamsa Transit:

- Navamsa Jupiter aspect the transit Jupiter.
- Navamsa Mercury and Transit Mercury are in the same sign. Mercury is in the Navamsa Ascendant.
- The Venus in Navamsa 5th house.

Conclusion:

- There are many methods to find out the timing of Marriage; still we could discuss some of the rules and ways here.
- The timing of Marriage found out approximately to some extent. It should be compared with few nearby dates suitable for Marriage.
- If in the Natal chart the planets support for the marriage, and then the support of the above methods mentioned definitely help us to find out the timing of marriage.(approximately within 15 to one month period) Om thath sath.

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